

Multiple crises: responses in agricultural law Polish report¹

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Abstract

L'accumulation des phénomènes de crise au cours des dernières années, provoqués principalement par la pandémie de Covid-19, mais aussi par la guerre en Ukraine, nécessite l'adaptation des outils juridiques existants à de nouveaux défis. Notre attention se portera bien sûr sur les instruments juridiques étroitement liés au droit agricole. Il ne fait cependant aucun doute que ces instruments ne peuvent être analysés indépendamment des conditions/déterminants politiques et sociaux. Il convient de souligner que les mécanismes juridiques utilisés jusqu'à présent, tant dans le cadre du droit communautaire au sens large que dans celui du droit national correspondant, s'avèrent insuffisants dans une situation de crise, et c'est sans aucun doute la situation à laquelle nous sommes confrontés.

Die Häufung von Krisenphänomenen in den letzten Jahren, die vor allem durch die Covid-19-Pandemie, aber auch durch den Krieg in der Ukraine verursacht wurden, erfordert die Anpassung der bestehenden Rechtsinstrumente an neue Herausforderungen. Unser Augenmerk gilt natürlich den Rechtsinstrumenten, die eng mit dem Agrarrecht verbunden sind. Es kann jedoch kein Zweifel daran bestehen, dass diese Instrumente nicht unabhängig von politischen und sozialen Bedingungen/Determinanten analysiert werden können. Es ist zu betonen, dass sich die bisher genutzten Rechtsmechanismen, sowohl im Rahmen des weit verstandenen EU-Rechts als auch des damit verbundenen nationalen Rechts, in einer Krisensituation als unzureichend erweisen, und das ist zweifellos die Situation, mit der wir es zu tun haben.

Introduction

The accumulation of crisis phenomena in recent years, caused primarily by the Covid-19 pandemic, but also by the war in Ukraine, requires the adaptation of existing legal tools to new challenges.

¹ This National Report was prepared for Commission I at the XXXI European Congress and Colloquium of Agricultural Law of CEDR from 6 to 9 September 2023 in Cardiff.

Our attention will, of course, be focused on legal instruments closely related to agricultural law. There can be no doubt, however, that these instruments cannot be analyzed independently from political and social conditions/determinants.

It should be emphasized that the legal mechanisms used so far, both within the framework of broadly understood EU law, but also the correlated national law, turn out to be insufficient in a crisis situation, and this is undoubtedly the situation we are dealing with.

Unfortunately, European Union countries are not able to develop a uniform legal system adequate to the emerging crisis situation in a short time, while continuing activities related to climate change and environmental protection. Moreover, the disturbing changes taking place in the political and legal systems of some countries, including Poland, make this task even more difficult. On the one hand, EU institutions, including the CJEU, are trying - within the framework of the available legal instruments - to persuade countries such as Poland, among others, to comply with basic EU standards, for example in the field of the judiciary, also at the level of the Constitutional Tribunal, but on the other hand, it is necessary to take into account the fact that the war in Ukraine is being waged in the immediate vicinity of Poland, which undoubtedly fulfills its obligations related to, for example, ensuring a safe stay for people affected by the effects of the armed conflict at the borders of the Union. The dilemmas that arise in this context require not only legal but also political action. A classic example is allowing Ukraine, with the modification of the existing legal instruments, to deliver agricultural products, including grain, to the territory of the European Union, including Poland. There is no doubt that the surplus of agricultural products, which was found in the area of e.g. Poland, was one of the reasons for the destabilization of the market and a significant drop in purchase prices.

Answering the formulated questions aimed at the preparation of the Country Report will require taking into account the conditions outlined at the beginning.

Impact of COVID-19 on agricultural production and agricultural markets

The Covid-19 pandemic resulted in serious problems in many regions of the world, including Poland. Restrictions in social and economic life introduced for health reasons also affected the functioning of agricultural production and agricultural markets. Certain pandemic phenomena such as:

- restrictions on the movement of people and goods and services, which negatively affected employment in the agricultural sector and international trade,
 - limitations in the functioning of hotel and catering enterprises, which resulted in a decrease in demand for food products,
 - deterioration of the situation on the labor market and a decrease in household income, which resulted in a decrease in expenditure on food products,
- contributed to a decline in agricultural and food production.

However, due to the need to ensure food security and the continuous demand of the population for food products, the pandemic crisis in the agricultural sector was less noticeable than in other sectors of the economy².

I.

In order to prevent the economic effects of the pandemic, changes were made to the RDP for 2014-2020, consisting in the introduction of a new measure: "Exceptional, temporary support for farmers, micro-enterprises, small and medium-sized enterprises." The main purpose of this support was to compensate at least part of the losses suffered by farmers as a result of the Covid-19 crisis and to help solve problems related to financial liquidity, threatening the continuity of agricultural activity in the sectors most affected by the pandemic. The aid concerned farms producing beef, milk, pigs, poultry, mutton, goats and ornamentals. 2% of the RDP funds for 2014-2020 were allocated to this measure. The aid could be granted only once, in the form of a lump sum, the amount of which depended on the type and volume of agricultural production and could not exceed EUR 7,000³.

There is also support for agricultural producers threatened with loss of financial liquidity as a result of restrictions on the agricultural market caused by Covid-19 in the maximum amount of 80% or 90% of the amount of the reduction in income from agricultural production⁴ and subsidies to the interest rate on loans granted to farmers⁵.

II.

In addition, in order to prevent the effects of the Covid-19 pandemic, including a decrease in demand for agricultural products and a significant increase in the prices of means of production, caused by the interruption of their supply chains, the Council of Ministers, by the regulation of July 14, 2020 amending the regulation on the detailed scope and methods of implementing certain tasks of the Agency Restructuring and Modernization of Agriculture⁶ introduced special financial assistance for agricultural producers who were threatened with loss of financial liquidity due to restrictions on the agricultural market due to the Covid-19 epidemic. Such aid was granted by way of a decision of the head of the poviát office of the Agency for Restructuring and Modernization of Agriculture.

The Agency for Restructuring and Modernization of Agriculture also introduced two aid programs aimed at supporting the market of specific agricultural products. The first involved financial assistance

² Data presented by P. Szajner, Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the situation on agricultural markets in Poland, Insurance in Agriculture. Materials and Studies, 1 (73)/2020, pp. 73-93.

³ Regulation of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development of August 24, 2020 on the detailed conditions and procedure for granting and disbursing financial aid for operations such as "Aid to farmers particularly affected by the COVID-19 crisis" under the measure "Exceptional temporary support for farmers, micro-enterprises and small enterprises and medium-sized enterprises particularly affected by the crisis related to COVID-19" covered by the Rural Development Program for 2014-2020, (Journal of Laws of 2020, item 1467).

⁴ Regulation of the Council of Ministers of January 27, 2015 on the detailed scope and methods of implementing certain tasks of the Agency for Restructuring and Modernization of Agriculture (Journal of Laws of 2015, item 187)

⁵ Act of 19.06.2020 on interest subsidies for bank loans granted to entrepreneurs affected by the effects of COVID-19 and on simplified procedure for approval of the arrangement in connection with the occurrence of COVID-19 (Journal of Laws of 2020, item 1086).

⁶ Journal of Law of 2020, item 1258.

to holders of fully mature chrysanthemums intended for sale who suffered losses due to market restrictions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. The second concerned financial assistance for pig producers who were threatened by the loss of financial liquidity due to restrictions caused by COVID-19.

From the above programs in 2020-2021, ARMA paid a total of PLN 602.1 million to agricultural producers affected by the COVID-19 crisis⁷.

III.

In addition, farmers are beneficiaries of the Act of March 2, 2020 on special solutions related to the prevention, counteracting and combating COVID-19, other infectious diseases and situations caused by them⁸, addressed to a wide range of entities, including entrepreneurs, public administration bodies, organizations public benefit, natural and legal persons. In response to the pandemic, the Polish legislator decided that due to the threat of spreading SARS-CoV-2 virus infections, there is a need to introduce special solutions that would allow taking measures to minimize the risk to public health. They supplement the basic regulations contained in particular in the Act of 5 December 2008 on preventing and combating infections and infectious diseases in humans⁹.

In particular, it provides:

- care allowance for persons covered by farmers' social insurance who, due to the closure of a nursery, children's club, kindergarten, school or other facility attended by a child or the inability to provide care by a nanny or day carer due to COVID-19, are obliged to exercise personal care for a child up to eight years of age, a child with disabilities or a child requiring special education (Article 4a),
- an allowance in the amount of 50% of the minimum remuneration for work for an insured farmer and household member, in the event of mandatory quarantine, epidemiological supervision or hospitalization in connection with COVID-19 (Article 31zy.3),
- exemption from the obligation to pay pension and disability insurance contributions for the second quarter of 2020 (Article 31 zz),
- extending the validity of certificates of partial incapacity for work, total incapacity for work, total incapacity for work and incapacity for independent existence, incapacity for independent existence (Article 15 zc).

The said act also provides for instruments to mitigate the effects of the pandemic in the economic sphere, including the agricultural and agri-food sectors.

These are: co-financing of part of the costs of running a business for entrepreneurs who are natural persons who do not employ employees (Article 15zzc), co-financing of part of the costs of salaries and social security contributions of employees (Article 15zzb), tax and payment reliefs (Articles 15zzze,

⁷ A. Jędruchiewicz, State policy towards agriculture in connection with the COVID-19 pandemic, *Horizon of Politics* 45, p. 106.

⁸ *Journal of Law* of 2021, item 2095 as amended.

⁹ *Journal of Law* of 2022, item 1657 as amended.

15zzzf, 15zzzg), deferral of tax payment deadlines (Article 15q), exemption from social security contributions if the agricultural producer employed employees (Article 31zo).

IV.

On June 1, 2022, the European Commission adopted the National Recovery and Resilience Plan. This opens up the possibility of obtaining non-repayable grants and loans, which should strengthen the Polish economy and make it easier to endure any crises. Part of the funds from the European Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) will be allocated to rural development, including in the form of grants, e.g. for storage centers for agricultural products and agri-food products, support for investments in agriculture, support for the construction of silos, construction and modernization of laboratories in the plant breeding sector and loans for sustainable water management in rural areas. So far, however, no money from KPO has been sent to Poland due to reservations regarding the implementation of the so-called milestones concerning e.g. the rule of law. The greatest reservations concern the judiciary, but also the anti-corruption framework and media pluralism and freedom.

The impact of the war in Ukraine on polish agriculture – selected issues

Russia's aggression against Ukraine has had a negative impact on agricultural activity not only in Ukraine itself, but also in Poland and other European Union countries. For example, the prices of fuels, energy, fertilizers and plant protection products have increased. The abolition of tariffs by the European Union on some Ukrainian agricultural products resulted in cheap grain entering the Polish and European markets, which made it difficult to sell domestic agricultural products. The solution to these problems was the subject of talks between the states and representatives of the European Union, which resulted in the adoption of appropriate legal acts.

On March 12, 2022, the Polish law on assistance to Ukrainian citizens in connection with the armed conflict on the territory of this country was passed¹⁰. It sets out specific rules for legalizing the stay of Ukrainian citizens, i.e. those who came to the territory of the Republic of Poland from the territory of Ukraine in connection with military operations conducted in the territory of that country, or holders of the Pole's Card who, together with their immediate family, arrived on the territory of the Republic of Poland due to these military operations. The Act also defines specific rules for entrusting work to Ukrainian citizens residing legally in the territory of the Republic of Poland; establishing the Assistance Fund to finance or subsidize the implementation of tasks to help Ukrainian citizens. Selected regulations of this legal act refer to issues related to agricultural activity, e.g. aid during the harvest. It is also worth noting that Ukrainian citizens can also conclude employment or mandate contracts and legally work in Poland in the agricultural and food industry.

In response to Russia's ongoing aggression against Ukraine, Poland has opened its borders to Ukrainians and accepted the largest number of refugees compared to other countries in Europe and in the world. Since February 24, 2022, the day the Russian aggression began, over 10.5 million people from Ukraine have crossed the Polish-Ukrainian border. Most of them are women and children. According to rough estimates, more than 1 million refugees from Ukraine are residing in Poland, in addition to

¹⁰ Polish Journal of Law 2022 item. 583 with amendments.

the same number of Ukrainians who arrived in the country before February 24, 2022. Poland continues to support Ukraine's efforts to join the European Union¹¹ and NATO.

There is no doubt that the position of the Polish agricultural producer in the food supply chain has been weakened. Liquidity problems have arisen that threaten the continuity of the activities of farmers and small businesses active in the processing, marketing distribution of agricultural products. The Polish government has taken a number of actions in recent months to solve the problems of agricultural producers resulting from Russia's aggression against Ukraine. Although it is impossible to cover all these actions due to the limited scope of this paper, it is worth highlighting that in response to the increase in fertilizer prices caused by the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic and Russia's aggression against Ukraine, on March 17, 2022, the Council of Ministers issued a regulation amending the regulation on the detailed scope and operation of the Agency for Restructuring and Modernization of Agriculture¹².

Pursuant to this legal act, the Agency for Restructuring and Modernization of Agriculture provided financial support to agricultural producers to co-finance the purchase in the period from September 1, 2021 to May 15, 2022 of mineral fertilizers other than fertilizer lime and fertilizer lime containing magnesium from entities operating in marketing or the sale of fertilizers. The aid rate was PLN 500 per hectare of agricultural land, except for grasses on arable land, and PLN 250 per hectare of meadows, pastures and grasses on arable land.

The European Union supports Ukraine, and at the same time tries to solve the problems of EU agricultural producers, especially those whose farms are located in countries bordering Ukraine. In the preamble to Regulation (EU) 2022/1033 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 June 2022 amending Regulation (EU) No 1305/2013 as regards a specific measure to provide exceptional temporary support under the European Agricultural Fund for Area Development (EAFRD) in response to the impact of the Russian invasion of Ukraine¹³, it was emphasized that "Farmers and rural businesses in the Union have been affected by the consequences of Russia's invasion of Ukraine in an unprecedented manner. Increasing input prices, particularly for energy, fertiliser and animal feed, have created economic disruption to the Union's agricultural sector and rural communities and have led to liquidity problems for farmers and small rural businesses active in processing, marketing or development of agricultural products"¹⁴. It was indicated that in the extraordinary situation arising in the agricultural

¹¹ On Thursday, March 3, the Polish Sejm adopted a resolution by acclamation on supporting Ukraine's membership in the European Union. In response to the request of the Ukrainian side, the deputies appealed to the EU Council to start the procedure of granting Ukraine the status of a candidate country and called on the European Commission to prepare a roadmap for accession negotiations and Ukraine's integration with the EU. "The Sejm calls on all EU institutions and Member States to enable Ukraine to join the European Union as soon as possible," they added. MEPs also asked the EU to include Ukraine in the European Recovery and Resilience Facility, as well as to create a separate fund to support the reconstruction of war damage, <https://www.sejm.gov.pl/Sejm9.nsf/komunikat.xsp?documentId=AEB16A40D1173D73C12587FA005881A9> As on: [accessed: 02.12.2022].

¹² Polish Journal of Laws 2022, item 642.

¹³ Official Journal of the European Union L 2022.173.34.

¹⁴ See also the Opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee on 'Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EU) No 1305/2013 as regards a specific measure to provide exceptional temporary support under the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) in response to the impact of Russia's invasion of Ukraine' (COM(2022) 242 final — 2022/0166 (COD))"

and food sectors, the objective of providing support could not be sufficiently achieved by the Member States. Therefore, in accordance with the principle of subsidiarity set out in Art. 5 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, due to the scale or effects of the action, the objective could be better achieved at Union level. Such activity complies with the principle of proportionality, as it does not go beyond what is necessary to achieve this objective (Regulation No. 2022/1033).

According to the EU regulation the support provided by the Member States shall contribute to food security or address market imbalances and shall support farmers or SMEs engaging in one or more of the following activities pursuing those goals: (a) circular economy; (b) nutrient management; (c) efficient use of resources; and (d) environmental and climate friendly production methods. On the basis of the discussed Regulation No. 2022/1033, Regulation (EU) No 1305/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on support for rural development by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 1698/2005, was amended with the insertion of art 39c, entitled "Extraordinary temporary support to farmers and SMEs particularly affected by the impact of the Russian invasion of Ukraine". The maximum amount of support could not exceed EUR 15,000 per farmer and EUR 100,000 per SME. The amendment of the EU regulation allowed the introduction of aid for agricultural producers in the Member States of the European Union (Regulation No. 2022/1033).

Due to the amendment of the EU regulation, on November 4, 2022, the Act amending the Act on supporting rural development with the participation of the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development under the Rural Development Program for 2014-2020 and was introduced¹⁵. On its basis, in the Act of February 20, 2015¹⁶ has been amended with the addition of art. 3, point 13aa, which provides for exceptional temporary support for farmers, micro, small and medium-sized enterprises particularly affected by the impact of the Russian invasion of Ukraine. Financial assistance for agricultural pig producers who meet certain conditions is regulated in the Regulation of the Minister of Agriculture and Development of December 16, 2022 on detailed conditions and procedures for granting and payment of financial assistance under the operation "Aid to farmers particularly affected by the effects of the Russian invasion to Ukraine" under the action "Extraordinary temporary support for farmers, micro, small and medium-sized enterprises particularly affected by the Russian invasion of Ukraine". This aid is covered by the Rural Development Program for 2014-2020¹⁷. From January 18 to February 7, 2023, farmers could submit "Applications for aid for farmers particularly affected by the impact of the Russian invasion of Ukraine"¹⁸.

Polish producers of cereals and oilseeds face great difficulties in selling their products on the domestic market. Ukrainian agricultural products were sold to processors in Poland, and their price was much

(COM(2022) 242 final - 2022/0166 (COD)), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52022AE2797>

¹⁵ Polish Journal of Laws 2022 item 2433.

¹⁶ Act of 20 February 2015 on supporting rural development from the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development under the Rural Development Program for 2014-2020; Polish Journal of Law from 2022 r. item 2422, 2433, 2727, from 2023, item 412.

¹⁷ <https://ekonomika.kpodr.pl/category/prow/>. [accessed: 29.04.2023 r.].

¹⁸ www.gov.pl/web/arimr/nadzwyczajne-tymczasowe-wsparcie-dla-rolnikow-mikroprzedsiębiorstw-oraz-malych-i-srednich-przedsiębiorstw-szczegolnie-dotknietych-wplywem-rosyjskiej-inwazji-na-ukraine--nabor-wydłużony-do-7-lutego-2023-r. [accessed: 29.06.2023 r.].

lower due to lower cultivation costs in Ukraine and the abolition of customs duties. In addition, Ukrainian agriculture is based mainly on large capital companies with foreign participation, which translates into lower costs of agricultural activity compared to Polish small producers. As has been repeatedly pointed out after the invasion of Russia, the costs associated with farming in Poland, in the form of electricity, gas, fuel and fertilizers, have increased significantly. Many agricultural producers provide assistance to Ukrainian citizens, offering them a place to live and work on their farms. However, due to problems with the sale of their own agricultural products, they are in a difficult financial situation.

As a result, farmers' protests began, and government officials held talks to find solutions. The Regulation of the Council of Ministers of 14 February 2023 amending the regulation on the detailed scope and methods of implementation of certain tasks of the Agency for Restructuring and Modernization of Agriculture¹⁹ indicated that in 2023 ARMR would provide financial assistance for the implementation of other tasks resulting from the state policy in the field of agriculture and rural development, to an agricultural producer: who incurred additional costs as a result of the instability on the wheat or corn market caused by the aggression of the Russian Federation against Ukraine. The ordinance stipulated that specified public aid may be granted to an agricultural producer from the date of announcement of a positive decision of the European Commission on the compatibility with the common market of the public aid specified in this provision.

On April 21, 2023, another Regulation of the Council of Ministers was signed by the Agency for Restructuring and Modernization of Agriculture, this time on the implementation of tasks related to the establishment of a support measure in emergency situations for the cereals and oilseeds sectors²⁰. It defines the tasks performed by this Agency related to the provision of assistance referred to in Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2023/739 of 4 April 2023 establishing an emergency support measure for the cereals and oilseeds sectors in Bulgaria, Poland and Romania²¹. According to this EU regulation, a total of EUR 56 300 000 of Union aid is made available to Bulgaria, Poland and Romania to provide exceptional support to farmers producing the cereals and oilseeds referred to in the Annex, subject to the conditions laid down in this Regulation. These countries use the above amounts for measures to compensate farmers for the economic losses caused by the increased imports of cereals and oilseeds from Ukraine in the affected regions. The funds were to be paid out on the basis of objective and non-discriminatory criteria, taking into account the economic losses suffered by the affected farmers. It is essential that payments do not create any market or competition distortions.

According to the Polish Regulation of the Council of Ministers of April 21, 2023, an agricultural producer may obtain aid if the conditions set out in this regulation are met. This executive act was then modified by the regulation of the Council of Ministers of May 16, 2023 amending the regulation on the implementation by the Agency for Restructuring and Modernization of Agriculture of tasks related to the establishment of an emergency support measure for the cereals and oilseeds sectors²².

Two EU regulations are worth mentioning. Firstly, Regulation (EU) 2023/1077 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 31 May 2023 on temporary trade-liberalization measures supplementing

¹⁹ Polish Journal of Laws 2023, item 308.

²⁰ Polish Journal of Law 2023 item. 762.

²¹ Official Journal of the European Union L 96 from 05.04.2023, p. 80.

²² Polish Journal of Law 2023 item. 928.

trade concessions applicable to Ukrainian products under the Association Agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their Member States, as one party, and Ukraine as the other party. It entered into force on June 6, 2023 and applies until June 5, 2024.

Secondly, the Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2023/1100 of 5 June 2023 introduced preventive measures concerning certain products originating in Ukraine. In point 6 of the Preamble, it was indicated that the assessment showed that important logistical bottlenecks still remain. In particular, the infrastructure in Bulgaria, Hungary, Poland, Romania and Slovakia remains insufficient to handle the surge in traffic, notably at the borders between Ukraine and those Member States. Equipment is still urgently needed and storage capacity is scarce, resulting in high logistics costs, while there is also a high risk of insufficient storage capacities in the affected Member States. It is emphasized in point 10 of the Preamble that “In order to swiftly address the exceptional circumstances rendering this Regulation necessary, a Joint Coordination Platform has been set up to coordinate the efforts of the Commission, Bulgaria, Hungary, Poland, Romania and Slovakia, as well as Ukraine and Moldova to improve the flow of trade between the Union and Ukraine including transit along corridors of agricultural products. The Joint Coordination Platform will deliver operational solutions to improve procedures, infrastructure and logistic bottlenecks between Ukraine and the Union by, accelerating and improving control procedures at borders, better coordinated transit, enhanced infrastructure and lowered overall logistics costs, thereby ensuring that wheat, maize, rapeseed (colza) and sunflower seed originating in Ukraine can move deeper into the Union and beyond as needed”.

Article 1 of Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2023/1100 of 5 June 2023 provides that the release for free circulation or the placing under the customs warehousing procedure, the free zone procedure or the inward processing procedure of products originating in Ukraine listed in the Annex to this Regulation shall only be allowed on the territory of Member States other than Bulgaria, Hungary, Poland, Romania or Slovakia. The regulation entered into force on the day of its publication in the Official Journal of the European Union and applies until September 15, 2023. Until September 15, 2023, the EU ban on imports of these agricultural products to Poland was extended. Their transit through the territory of the Republic of Poland will still be allowed.

Poland supports Ukraine in its struggle for independence and future membership in the European Union. However, Ukraine should also take steps to amend its legislation. Family farms play an important role in achieving the objectives of the EU's common agricultural policy. Such farms prevail in the European Union. It is a valuable sustainable model in social, economic terms and for environmental matters. In Ukraine, agri-companies are popular, and these entities lease more than 60% of agricultural land. In 2019, individual farmers used only 27% of the land²³. For the transformation of agrarian structure, the development of family farms are necessary in the context of future integration with the European Union. There is a lack of appropriate legal provisions to support the development of the family farm model in Ukraine, both in terms of insurance and financial support, as well as the lease and purchase of agricultural real estate.

²³ See more A. Suchoń, A. Bilochenko, *Agrarian structure in Poland and Ukraine (history, present state and future)*. CEDR Journal of Rural Law , 2022, 1, 54-65.

Energy crisis

Energy is essential for the functioning of the whole of society and running business, including agriculture. Due to climate change, environmental protection and the preservation of natural resources for future generations, energy from renewable sources is taken on increased importance. Russia's invasion of Ukraine and climate change have resulted in greater concern for Poland's energy security. It is significant to become independent from fossil fuels and exclude supplies of energy resources from Russia. Currently, Poland no longer has contracts for the supply of gas from Russia. However, the high price of energy has become a problem for many farms, households and entrepreneurs, including those operating in rural areas. In accordance with the "National Energy Policy until 2040" adopted by the Council of Ministers (PEP 2040), domestic electricity consumption will increase by 22% by 2030 and by 37% by 2040²⁴. The basic legal acts related to energy are the Act of February 20, 2015 on renewable energy sources²⁵, the Act of April 10, 1997 Energy Law²⁶, and the Regulation of the Minister of Climate and Environment of March 23, 2022 on the registration, balancing and sharing measurement data and settlements of energy cooperatives²⁷.

The Council Regulation (EU) 2022/2577 of 22 December 2022, establishing a framework for accelerating the implementation of renewable energy solutions²⁸, states "the Russian Federation's war of aggression against Ukraine (...) threatens the security of supply in the Union and its Member States. (...) The rapid implementation of solutions in the field of renewable energy sources can contribute to mitigating the effects of the current energy crisis by creating a defense against Russia's actions". The aforementioned Council Regulation (EU) 2022/2577 of 22 December 2022 emphasized the importance of emergency provisions aimed at accelerating the permitting procedure applicable to the production of energy from renewable sources.

It should also be pointed out that the issues of renewable energy have been addressed in the Polish Strategic Plan for the CAP 2023-2027²⁹. Agricultural producers will be able to benefit from programs encouraging investment in activities related to renewable energy, association and enabling the implementation of many challenges indicated in the European Green Deal. An example is the possibility of applying for EU funds for the construction of: agricultural biogas plants; installations producing energy from solar radiation, together with energy storage and energy management systems, as well as systems improving the energy efficiency of farm buildings used for agricultural production (including thermal modernization, biomass boilers, heat recovery systems); and installations producing energy from renewable energy sources. On farms, agricultural producers are increasingly implementing investments in the field of renewable energy, e.g. biomass boilers, photovoltaic panels, photovoltaic collectors, micro biogas plants, small wind turbines, or heat pumps. Particularly high popularity in recent years is associated with photovoltaics. The possibility of obtaining subsidies or taking advantage of

²⁴ Obwieszczenie Ministra Klimatu i Środowiska z 2 marca 2021 r. w sprawie polityki energetycznej państwa do 2040 r., M.P. 2021, poz. 264. <https://www.dziennikustaw.gov.pl/M2021000026401.pdf> [accessed: 22.03.2023].

²⁵ Journal of Laws of 2022, item 1378.

²⁶ Journal of Laws of 2022, item 1385.

²⁷ Journal of Laws of 2022, item 703.

²⁸ Official Journal of the European Union L 335, 29.12.2022, p. 36–44.

²⁹ <https://www.gov.pl/web/wprpo2020/zatwierdzony-przez-komisje-europejska-plan-strategiczny-dla-wspolnej-polityki-rolnej-na-lata-2023-2027> [accessed: 22.03.2023].

investment relief in agricultural tax, climate change and, as a rule, more and more sunny days, is conducive to the implementation of these investments. Photovoltaics depend on the sun's rays, which, however, do not occur continuously throughout the year. There is no doubt, however, that they do not provide as much stability in terms of energy supply as biogas plants. Renewable energy allows people running a farm to reduce running costs, which is particularly important in the case of breeding, e.g. cattle and milk production.

Agricultural tax payers (mainly agricultural producers) who carry out investments in the field of RES may benefit from agricultural tax relief. According to Art. 13 of the Agricultural Tax Act, agricultural tax payers are entitled to investment relief for expenses incurred related to the purchase and installation of equipment for the use of natural energy sources for production purposes (wind, biogas, sun, water drop) - if these expenses were not financed in whole or in part with public funds.

On March 9, 2023, the Act amending the Act on investments in wind farms and certain other acts was passed. The Act specifies the conditions and mode of locating, building and rebuilding wind farms; rules and method of consulting with the local community on the location of wind farms; rules for locating new residential buildings in the vicinity of wind farms; and the rules for the participation of the commune's inhabitants in the benefits resulting from the location of wind farms.

The new Act of July 13, 2023 on facilitating the preparation and implementation of investments in the field of agricultural biogas plants, as well as their operation, defines specific rules and procedures for the preparation and implementation of agricultural biogas plants and the rules of procedure for issuing a decision on the construction permit for agricultural biogas plants, aimed at facilitating and accelerating the preparation and implementation of investments, as well as the conditions for conducting activities in these biogas plants. Article 3 of this Act indicates that the entity authorized to prepare and implement investments in the field of agricultural biogas plants is an entity that, for example, runs a farm or a special department of agricultural production as part of agricultural activity; being a group of agricultural producers or a producer organisation, an energy cooperative or a cooperative of farmers. The provisions of the Act specify that they apply to agricultural biogas plants in which only the following substrates are used to produce agricultural biogas, electricity from agricultural biogas, heat from agricultural biogas or biomethane from agricultural biogas, e.g. agricultural products and agricultural by-products, including animal waste; products from the processing of products of agricultural origin and by-products, waste or residues from this processing, including food processing and production,

To sum up, it should be stated that the Polish legislator attaches increasing importance to increasing the share of renewable energy in Poland. The efforts of the legislator in this area can be observe.

Since 2019 Poland has intensified efforts in order to develop distributed energy system in which renewable energy sources play a significant role. The reasons for that strategical movement are: (1) reaction of Polish state authorities to Russian aggression on Ukraine, (2) the necessity of meeting the obligations of EU policy regarding energy transition and achieving climate neutrality.

The objective of developing distributed energy system, according to the Polish legislator should be met by supporting the emergence of the social initiatives that carry out investments in renewable energy sources. Such initiatives are part of community energy movement, which promotes the construction of a distributed energy system by citizens, in particular those associated within local communities,

who take an active part in energy generation and its management. In that aspect, Poland as a Member State of European Union has partially fulfilled the obligations to transpose EU directives: Directive (EU) 2018/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources (L 328/82) and Directive (EU) 2019/944 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on common rules for the internal market for electricity and amending Directive 2012/27/EU (L 158/125) by (1) providing incentives and support system for renewable energy prosumers (2) introducing citizen energy communities to the Polish legal system.

The number of prosumer installations in Poland has increased rapidly since 2019. According to data as of April 2023, 1 254 169 micro-installations were connected to the distribution grid in Poland³⁰, recording an increase of almost twelve times compared to 30 September 2019. (at that time, the number of micro-installations connected to the distribution network was 106 117)³¹. Such rapid growth of the number of prosumers was mainly caused by favourable support system (net metering, changed in 2021 to net-billing system) and public financing scheme for prosumer installations.

In June of 2023 lower house of Polish parliament has passed the amendment to the energy law act³². This legislation introduce citizen energy community to the Polish legal system and thus is the fulfilment of the obligation to implement IEMD directive. According to its legal definition citizen energy community is an entity having legal personality with a broad scope of economic activity, i.a. generation, consumption, distribution, sales, trading, aggregation, and storage of electricity. Currently, before the act will come into the force, it also has to be passed by the higher house of the Polish parliament and it has to be signed by the president. It also should be noted, that citizen energy communities will be established in Poland, only if legislator will provide regulation granting them a fair access to the energy grid and effective support system.

Until the aforementioned amendment to the energy law act, in Poland energy communities could operate mainly in two legal forms: (1) as energy cooperatives and (2) as energy clusters. Energy cooperative is a cooperative, which scope of activity consists of generation of energy from renewable sources for the benefit of its members. Energy cluster is a civil agreement which parties decide to act together as a joint initiative to develop renewable energy sources installations.

Comparing the development of indicated legal forms of citizen energy, there is currently a more dynamic emergence of energy cooperatives. This state of affairs is mainly caused by the fact that Polish legislator has provided energy cooperatives with an effective support system - net-metering and recently announced public financing projects. As of July 2023, in Poland there are 10 registered energy cooperatives – 2 registered in 2021 and 8 in 2023. They utilize only photovoltaic installations and their total installed electrical capacity is 3,455 Mwe.

Community energy initiatives have not appeared on a large scale in Poland so far. Thus, the current stage of community energy development can be described as mainly popularisation of the concept of

³⁰ Mikroinstalacje w Polsce, Raport PTPiREE <http://www.ptpiree.pl/energetyka-w-polsce/energetyka-w-liczbach/mikroinstalacje-w-polsce>

³¹ Produkcja energii elektrycznej z odnawialnych źródeł energii, Rynek Elektryczny, <https://www.rynekelektryczny.pl/energia-elektryczna-ze-zrodel-odnawialnych/>

³² Rządowy projekt ustawy o zmianie ustawy - Prawo energetyczne oraz niektórych innych ustaw, druk nr 3237, <https://www.sejm.gov.pl/sejm9.nsf/PrzebiegProc.xsp?nr=3237>

social participation in the energy sector. Further growth of community energy depends on relevant support for such initiatives, which should be provided by the Polish legislator.

Climate change

The agricultural sector in Poland is of great social and economic importance. The relationship between agriculture and climatic conditions is far-reaching, as a result of which the predicted and observed climate change arouses considerable interest³³. The climate crisis translates into an increase in prices on global agricultural markets (EP Resolution, 2022/2593(RSP)).

Climate change and biodiversity loss have direct and indirect impacts on the agri-food and aquatic food sectors (EP resolution 2022/2593(RSP)). A direct impact is one that results from changes in climatic conditions that determine yields (thermal changes, changes in the spatial and time distribution of precipitation and soil moisture, and changes in the frequency and intensity of extreme weather events)³⁴. The indirect impact on productivity in agriculture results from various plant responses to factors that are not indifferent to climate change, such as: cultivation, fertilization, appearance and yield of weeds, pathogens and pests. The implication of the observed climate changes are also new environmental effects for agriculture, including, for example, soil erosion in conditions of more frequent intensive rainfall or degradation of organic matter in soils accompanying deep and prolonged drought. The productivity of crops is also determined by the increase in the atmospheric concentration of carbon dioxide and ozone in the lower layer of the troposphere³⁵. The latest Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) report outlines how threats to food security and nutrition are materializing and will continue to grow³⁶. Interpretation of the links between agriculture and climate change is complicated and multi-threaded. Climate change can be beneficial for some crops and crops, and unfavorable for others. Agriculture itself is a factor leading to climate change (contributing to greenhouse gas emissions) and at the same time it is an ally in limiting these changes (by binding carbon dioxide)³⁷.

Polish agriculture has been operating in the conditions of climate change for a long time, while experiencing higher climatic threats (for example, in 2006, 2011 and 2015, serious decreases in yields were recorded). In Poland, climate change also brings some opportunities (for example - an increase in the chances of growing thermophilic plants). Undoubtedly, climate change had an impact on the market after the pandemic, although this problem also applies to the period before. The currently dominant model of agriculture in Poland assumes the maximization of yields based on highly efficient

³³ Kundzewicz Z.W. i Kozyra J. (2017) Wpływ zmian klimatu na rolnictwo w Polsce W: *Zmiany klimatu i ich wpływ na wybrane sektory w Polsce*. Kundzewicz Z.W., Hov Ø., Okruszko T. (Red.), Poznań 2017, Rozdział 11, 168-181.

³⁴ Tubiello F.N., Soussana J.F. i Howden S.M. (2007) Crop and pasture response to climate change. *PNAS*, 104, 19686-19690.

³⁵ Gornall J., Betts R., Burke E., Clark R., Camp J., Willett K. i Wiltshire A. (2010) Implications of climate change for agricultural productivity in the early twenty-first century. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. B* 365:2973-2989.

³⁶ Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability | Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability (ipcc.ch)

³⁷ Kundzewicz Z.W. i Kozyra J. (2017) Wpływ zmian klimatu na rolnictwo w Polsce W: *Zmiany klimatu i ich wpływ na wybrane sektory w Polsce*. Kundzewicz Z.W., Hov Ø., Okruszko T. (Red.), Poznań 2017, Rozdział 11, 168-181.

production technology, with intensive plant protection. To meet the challenges of climate change for agriculture, Poland has taken measures in the short and medium term.

It should be pointed out that the issue of environmental protection has already been referred to by the Polish legislator several times in the Basic Law, namely Art. 5, art. 68 sec. 4, art. 74 and Art. 86 of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland³⁸.

In the medium term, on July 16, 2019, the Council of Ministers adopted the "National Environmental Policy 2030 - Development Strategy in the Area of Environment and Water Management" (PEP2030)³⁹. The role of the Policy is to ensure Poland's ecological security and high quality of life for all residents. The policy strengthens the government's activities consisting in building an innovative economy in compliance with the principles of sustainable development. The state environmental policy 2030 is a strategy within the meaning of the Act on the principles of development policy, as well as one of the nine strategies constituting the foundation for managing the development of the country. In the system of strategic documents, it specifies the Strategy for Responsible Development until 2020 (with a perspective until 2030). PEP2030 is the basis for investing European funds in the financial perspective for 2021-2027. The strategy also supports the implementation of Poland's goals and commitments at the international level, including at the EU and UN levels, especially in the context of the goals of the EU's climate and energy policy until 2030 and the goals of sustainable development included in the 2030 Agenda.

In addition to PEP2030, one of the nine strategies for managing the development of the country, important from the perspective of the challenges generated by the agricultural sector, is the Strategy for Sustainable Development of Rural Areas, Agriculture and Fisheries 2030 (SZRWiR 2030)⁴⁰. Its main objective is the economic development of the countryside, enabling a sustainable increase in the income of its inhabitants while minimizing economic, social and territorial stratification and improving the condition of the natural environment. The strategy is the basic strategic document of the country's agricultural and rural development policy, presenting the objectives, directions of intervention and actions that should be undertaken in the perspective of 2030.

The Ministry of Maritime Economy and Inland Navigation also developed, with the participation of the State Water Holding Polish Waters, the State Hydrological and Meteorological Service, the State Hydrogeological Service and the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, a draft Assumptions for the Program for counteracting water scarcity for 2021-2027 with a perspective until 2030 (PPNW)⁴¹. It includes measures to increase water retention and allow it to be retained in the environment for a long time. One of the three priorities of the PPNW is to create conditions for the sustainable use of water resources, also in the field of agriculture.

In the short term, on July 14, 2020, the Council of Ministers adopted a resolution on granting consent to notify the European Commission of an aid program for agricultural producers who are at risk of losing financial liquidity, due to restrictions on the agricultural market related to the COVID-19 epidemic and the lack of payment of aid in the form of subsidies in connection with the occurrence of

³⁸ Journal of Laws of 1997, No. 78, item 483, as amended.

³⁹ Resolution No. 67 of the Council of Ministers of July 16, 2019.

⁴⁰ Resolution No. 123 of the Council of Ministers of October 15, 2019.

⁴¹ Resolution No. 92 of the Council of Ministers of September 10, 2019.

drought, hurricane, hail, torrential rain, spring frosts or floods in 2019. In addition, on May 4, 2023, a resolution of the Council of Ministers was adopted on granting consent to notify the European Commission of the aid program for the creation of the Agriculture Protection Fund.

Financial support under the EU Common Agricultural Policy for 2023-2027 is granted to Poland on the basis of the Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy for 2023-2027 (PS CAP)⁴². This support includes interventions in the form of direct payments and coupled support granted in 13 sectors. A new element of the direct payment system, supporting the implementation of practices beneficial for the environment, climate and animal welfare, are eco-schemes. Poland has included six eco-schemes in its strategic plan: animal welfare; carbon farming and nutrient management; areas with melliferous plants; conducting plant production in the Integrated Plant Production system; biological protection of crops; water retention on permanent grasslands. The plan provides for the possibility of combining individual eco-schemes within the farm, so as to ensure the most effective use of them. Transitional national support is also implemented. As part of rural development interventions, farmers can apply for payments for less-favoured areas (LFA), agri-environment-climate payments, green payments, as well as bonuses for afforestation and agro-forestry systems. In the CAP SP, the emphasis has been increased on investments for the environment and climate, animal welfare and production based on the highest standards. An important supplement to the catalog of support for farms is the possibility of using support based on various forms of cooperation and risk management tools.

Due to the need to ensure food security in the face of the war in Ukraine, EU regulations allowed Member States to take advantage of a temporary derogation from the application of the GAEC 7 standards in full and the GAEC 8 standard on the prohibition of production on fallow land (Commission Implementing Regulation, 2022/1317). In 2023, Poland benefited from a derogation in respect of both obligations, i.e.: implementation of the GAEC 7 standard and fallow land under the GAEC 8 standard (production may be carried out except for corn, soybean and short rotation coppice)⁴³.

In addition, in 2023, Poland extended the deadline for submitting applications for financial assistance under the PS CAP to June 30 (and with the application of a penalty - to July 25), the extended deadline is provided for direct payments, transitional national support, payments under environmental interventions, and other commitments in the field of management and payments for areas with natural or other specific constraints⁴⁴. As a measure to ensure that environmental standards applicable to farmers are not undermined, inter alia, through shipments to increase agricultural productivity and counteract market instability, the Regulation of the Council of Ministers of January 31, 2023 on the "Action program to reduce water pollution with nitrates from agricultural sources and to prevent further pollution" (Journal of Laws of 2023 item 244). The above scope should also include the Regulation of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development of 26 April 2023 on the detailed purpose, conditions and mode of providing support in the field of storage infrastructure to increase the resilience of farms

⁴² Journal of Laws of 2023, item 412.

⁴³ Regulation of the Minister of Agriculture and of March 10, 2023, Journal of Laws of 2023, item 478.

⁴⁴ Regulation of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development of May 11, 2023, Journal of Laws of 2023, item 907.

to crises under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan⁴⁵, the provisions of which were assessed as having a positive impact on the natural environment.

In the national context, there is no perceived risk that the focus on greater agricultural productivity may undermine the environmental standards applicable to the farmer. This situation is prevented by the implementing provisions to the CAP SPS Act, i.e. the Regulation of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development of March 13, 2023 on the detailed conditions and detailed procedure for granting and paying payments under climate and environmental schemes under the Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy for 2023-2027 (Journal of Laws of 2023, item 493), Regulation of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development of 31 March 2023 on detailed conditions and detailed procedure for granting and paying agri-environment-climate payments under the Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy for 2023-2027 (Journal of Laws of 2023, item 734) and the Regulation of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development of 20 April 2023 on the detailed conditions and detailed procedure for granting and paying out financial assistance under animal welfare schemes under the Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy for 2023-2027⁴⁶, introducing penalties for a farmer's failure to comply with the requirements for individual payments.

The need to increase the resilience of agricultural sectors to future shocks related to climate change is reflected in the Strategy for Responsible Development until 2020 (with a perspective until 2030) (Resolution No. 8 of the Council of Ministers of February 14, 2017) and the Strategic Adaptation Plan for sectors and sensitive areas to climate change by 2020 (with a perspective until 2030) which was adopted by the Council of Ministers on October 29, 2013. The plan defines the goals and directions of adaptation activities for sectors most vulnerable to climate change, including agriculture. It provides, among others, investment support for farms as well as training and technological consultancy taking into account the aspects of adapting agricultural production to increased climate risk and counteracting climate change, as well as the development of monitoring and early warning systems on the possible effects of climate change on plant and animal production.

Poland has not introduced changes to the PS CAP for the 2023-2027 programming period, including the suspension of environmental standards.

Safety nets and agricultural reserves

1. Agricultural reserves and mandatory stockpiling

Poland has a system of strategic reserves under the Act of December 17, 2020 on Strategic Reserves⁴⁷ and also a crisis management system. Crisis management issues are regulated by the Act of April 26, 2007 on crisis management⁴⁸. These are security systems that should serve to sustain the security of the state, including (at least it would seem so) food security, in emergency situations.

The issue of compulsory food stocks is part of the problem of strategic reserves, which are extremely important for the proper functioning of the state and the security of its citizens - especially in cases of

⁴⁵ Journal of Laws of 2023, item 820.

⁴⁶ Journal of Laws of 2023, item 797.

⁴⁷ Journal of Laws 2023, item 294.

⁴⁸ Journal of Laws of 2023, item 122.

unexpected disasters and crises, as the pandemic situation and the unjustified Russian invasion of Ukraine have clearly demonstrated in recent years.

Such an important function in the field of security, including food security, has been entrusted in Poland to an entity such as the Government Agency for Strategic Reserves (hereinafter: RARS). The legal basis for the operation of RARS are the provisions of the Act of 17 December 2020 on Strategic Reserves⁴⁹, which came into force on 23 February 2021, and the statute⁵⁰. Under the referenced Act, the former Material Reserve Agency was transformed into the Government Strategic Reserve Agency directly supervised by the Prime Minister. RARS constitutes an atypical administrative entity created to ensure the efficiency and effectiveness of the administration. RARS performs public tasks with a specific scope of subject matter, and it is to these tasks that both its structure and legal forms of operation are adapted. The creation of entities such as RARS is influenced by the current economic, social and political situation⁵¹.

Strategic reserves are products, raw materials, materials and equipment that fall into three basic categories: food, medical and technical reserves.

According to Article 3 of the Law on Strategic Reserves, strategic reserves are created in the event of a threat to state security and defense, security, public order and health, and the occurrence of a natural disaster or crisis situation, for the purposes of supporting the performance of tasks in the field of state security and defense, restoring critical infrastructure, mitigating disruptions in the continuity of supplies serving the functioning of the economy and meeting the basic needs of citizens, saving their lives and health, realizing the national interests of the Republic of Poland in the field of national security, fulfilling its international obligations, as well as providing assistance and support to entities of public international law.

In particular, strategic reserves can be raw materials, materials, equipment, machinery, structures, critical infrastructure elements, production power, service power, livestock, petroleum products, agricultural and agri-food products, foodstuffs and their components. Thus, among these products are agricultural products.

Food reserves are created to cope with disruptions in the continuity of supply to serve the functioning of the economy and meet the basic needs of citizens, and are activated, for example, in the event of a natural disaster or war.

Strategic reserves are a separate asset of the State Treasury. It is permissible to keep strategic reserves in the form of an assortment entrusted to public administration bodies or owned by entrepreneurs or non-entrepreneurs, in warehouses at their disposal.

The literature aptly points out that the legal-administrative obligation alone to create and maintain specific stocks is not sufficient to ensure state security. More often than not, no country is in a position to guarantee its full raw material requirements from accumulated reserves, requiring the construction

⁴⁹ Act of 17 December 2020 on strategic reserves, consolidated text: Journal of Laws 2023, item 294.

⁵⁰ Order No. 23 of the Prime Minister of 15 March 2021 on granting the statute of the Government Strategic Reserve Agency, M.P. 2021.281.

⁵¹ P. Bieś-Srokosz, The essence of creating new-typical entities in public administration in Poland. Selected issues [in:] *The Spirit of Rights in Central and Eastern Europe*, eds. M. Kępa, M. Marszał, Wrocław 2016, pp. 70-71.

and maintenance of cost-intensive warehouses, storage facilities, tanks and supporting infrastructure. For this reason, in addition to the stockpile obligation itself, appropriate procedures for activating and making available its reserves should also be examined. These will actually constitute the most important instrument for responding to crises in the national economy⁵².

There is no doubt that the Russian invasion of Ukraine exacerbated the global food crisis revealed during the COVID-19 pandemic. There was a sharp increase in the price of cereals, fertilisers, and some types of feed. Russia's invasion of Ukraine was a turning point for global food security.

Storage of strategic reserves is carried out both in the Strategic Reserve Agency's own warehouses (Article 15) and for a fee in private or public warehouses under storage contracts (Article 16). In addition, the agency may maintain strategic reserves owned by businesses or other entities under a paid contract (Article 17). It is also possible to conclude a capacity maintenance contract or a standby service contract (Article 18).

The Prime Minister, by decision, creates strategic reserves, as determined by the Program. The decision on the creation of strategic reserves shall include, at a minimum, the determination of the assortment and its quantity and the purpose of the strategic reserves to be created.

The decision to create strategic reserves is executed by the Strategic Reserve Agency. It purchases a certain amount of the assortment of strategic reserves and stores the purchased assortment, and enters into appropriate contracts.

The range and quantities of reserves are determined by the Government Strategic Reserve Program, which is being prepared for 5 years. The current one covers the years 2022-2026.

By way of example, until 14 April 2023, RARS conducted market research regarding the purchase of grain - consumption wheat - for strategic reserves. The subject of the discernment was the purchase of grain together with storage services in the country⁵³.

Detailed data on the assortment, quantities and distribution of maintained reserves constitute classified information, within the meaning of the Law on Protection of Classified Information of August 5, 2010⁵⁴.

2. Crisis management

Crisis management is the activity of public administration bodies that is part of national security management, which consists in preventing crisis situations, preparing to take control of them through planned actions, responding in case of crisis situations, removing their consequences and restoring critical resources and infrastructure.

Critical infrastructure includes systems and their constituent functionally related facilities, including construction facilities, equipment, installations, services that are key to the security of the state and its citizens and that serve to ensure the smooth functioning of public administration bodies, as well as

⁵² M. Grzywacz, *State raw material security. Instruments of administrative law*, Warsaw 2022, Legalis.

⁵³ <https://www.agropolska.pl/agrobiznes> [accessed:11.04.2023].

⁵⁴ Journal of Laws No. 182, item 1228.

institutions and businesses. Critical infrastructure includes, among others, food supply and water supply systems. The National Crisis Management Plan and provincial, district and municipal crisis management plans.

Food security activities are also part of securing food chains. These activities are:

- 1) Securing supply chains against natural disasters, epidemics or warfare,
- 2) Reducing food loss and waste,
- 3) Serving the competitiveness of agriculture, sustainable management of natural resources
- 4) Stabilizing agricultural production,
- 5) Integration of agri-food sector players, shortening the supply chain (supply and direct sales, agricultural retail trade).

Agri Insurances

Agricultural activities are subject to the impact of many external factors that determine their extent and magnitude. Consequently, they stimulate the income of agricultural producers and thus affect the sustainability of farming. To a large extent, they are independent of human will. Most often, they cannot be predicted or effectively counteracted. These factors constitute the broadly defined risk.

The specific nature of farming involves natural risks. These include variable climatic and biological conditions, soil conditions, plant and livestock diseases, the occurrence of pests, the seasonality of production, or the occurrence of extreme weather phenomena, such as drought or sudden precipitation, which contribute to crises in the extreme. In response to the negative effects of these risks, the EU legislator has proposed the use of certain legal instruments⁵⁵. Ultimately, the creation of an appropriate legal framework for risk management is left to the Member States, which, in accordance with local natural conditions, adopt appropriate legal instruments.

In Poland, the issues of risk management in agriculture through the application of specific legal instruments and mechanisms provided for in EU legislation are regulated by the Act of 7 July 2005 on insurance of agricultural crops and livestock⁵⁶.

The Act sets out the rules for: (1) the application of premium subsidies for the conclusion of insurance contracts against the risk of the consequences of random events in agriculture; (2) the conclusion and execution of contracts of compulsory insurance of crops against specific risks of the consequences of random events in agriculture; and (3) the provision of a targeted subsidy for the coverage of a part of compensation for damage caused by drought.

⁵⁵ Regulation (EU) 2021/2115 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 2 December 2021 establishing rules on support for strategic plans to be drawn up by Member States under the common agricultural policy (CAP Strategic Plans) and financed by the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF) and by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1305/2013 and (EU) No 1307/2013, PE/64/2021/REV/1, *OJ L 435*, 6.12.2021, pp. 1–186.

⁵⁶ Polish Journal of Laws 2019, item. 477.

On the basis of the Act on Insurance of Crops and Livestock in 2023, subsidies to premiums of agricultural producers for concluding insurance agreements against the occurrence of specified fortuitous events are applied from the state budget. For crop production, which includes the cultivation of the following crops: cereals, maize, rapeseed, canola, hops, tobacco, ground vegetables, fruit trees and bushes, strawberries, potatoes, sugar beet or leguminous plants from the occurrence of such risks as: hurricane, flood, torrential rain, hail, lightning, landslide, avalanche, drought, adverse winter effects or spring frost. However, for livestock production, including cattle, horses, sheep, goats, poultry or pigs, it covers contracts against the risks of: hurricane, flood, torrential rain, hail, lightning, landslide, avalanche, emergency slaughter.

To a certain extent, subsidised insurance should be considered as compulsory insurance. According to Article 10c of the Act, every farmer who has received direct payments to agricultural land, the so-called direct payments, is obliged to conclude a contract to insure at least 50% of the crop area against the risk of damage caused by: flood, drought, hail, negative effects of overwintering or spring frost⁵⁷. The obligation to insure crops applies to: cereals, maize, oilseed rape, colza, hops, tobacco, ground vegetables, fruit trees and bushes, strawberries, potatoes, sugar beet or leguminous plants, from sowing or planting to their harvest. The insurance contract covers the main crop as defined in the Act.

In order for the farmer to comply with the statutory obligation, he or she shall conclude an insurance contract with an insurance company of his or her choice, which has concluded an agreement with the minister responsible for agriculture on subsidies for the year in question⁵⁸. Subsidised crop insurance contracts are concluded until the limit of subsidies for a given year is exhausted.

The level of subsidies from the state budget to insurance premiums payable by agricultural producers for concluding an insurance contract for agricultural crops or livestock for 2023 was determined by the Council of Ministers in the Ordinance of 25 November 2022 on the level of subsidies to premiums for insurance of agricultural crops and livestock in 2023 in the amount of 65% of the premium for 1 ha of agricultural crops and 65% of the premium for 1 livestock animal⁵⁹. The crop insurance mechanism used in Poland is that the state may subsidise the farmer's premium by up to 65%, provided, however, that the tariff rate set by the insurance company does not exceed 9% of the sum insured.

The provisions of the Act give the farmer the option to insure crops against all risks specified in the Act, or those selected by the farmer and occurring most frequently in the area. In order to fulfil the statutory requirement, the coverage must include at least one of the listed risks, i.e.: flood, hail, drought, negative effects of overwintering or spring frost. For a surcharge on the premium, the farmer can also insure his crops against the risks of: hurricane, torrential rain, lightning, landslide and avalanche.

A farmer can seek compensation under the compulsory crop insurance when crop losses amount to at least 10%, and 25% in the case of a drought risk. At the same time, compensation for damage caused by risks other than drought may be reduced by no more than 10% of the value of such damage, while

⁵⁷ A farmer who fails to fulfil the obligation to conclude a compulsory insurance contract, i.e. at least 50% of the crop area, has to take into account the necessity to pay a fee for failing to fulfil this obligation. The amount of the fee, applicable in each calendar year, is the equivalent in PLN of EUR 2 per 1 ha, determined using the average exchange rate announced by the National Bank of Poland.

⁵⁸ There are currently eight insurance companies.

⁵⁹ Polish Journal of Laws 2022, item. 2468.

in the case of the occurrence of the risk of drought by 20%, 25% or 30% of the sum insured - depending on the amount of reduction (franchise) indicated in the insurance contract.

In the case of the aforementioned animals, premium subsidies are also applied for the following fortuitous events: hurricane, flood, driving rain, hail, lightning, landslide, avalanche and slaughter by necessity. In this case, the insurance contract may cover all the risks indicated above or selected by the agricultural producer. Subsidies will be available to agricultural producers of up to 65% of the premium (up to 1 head), in the event that insurance companies set insurance tariff rates on the total insurance of animals not exceeding 0.5% of the sum insured.

In summary, the system of crop and livestock insurance in Poland has not changed over the past years. The scope of contracts concluded and their conditions do not protect producers from risk. At the same time, the consequences of not taking out policies, do not favour the universality of this form of risk management. A major problem is the weakness of the system in the face of the frequent risk of drought. However, due to its frequent occurrence and the scale of damage resulting from it, insurance companies do not meet the needs of farmers and often refuse to conclude a contract. Thus, it should be concluded that the system of insurance of agricultural crops and livestock supported by public funds is still ineffective and not conducive to the stabilisation of agricultural production. It is only on the farmers' side that a certain simplification has been introduced in that, at his request, premiums can be deducted from the value of the direct payments granted.

A draft amendment to the law in question is due to be debated this year, although it will not change the assumed direction of risk management through insurance, but will only broaden the catalogue of crops.

Summary

The economic, social and legal conditions outlined in the introduction to this Report have been subject to a detailed analysis in its individual segments.

The ongoing legal considerations in the areas indicated in the Report allow us to draw conclusions. Of course, the dynamics of the ongoing changes does not allow us to assume that these conclusions will be final and exhaustive. It seems that they should become the basis for further discussion and the development of uniform rules for adapting the legal system to a crisis situation, both in the national and EU dimension.

It should be clearly emphasized that Poland, as a country directly adjacent to Ukraine, provides assistance to this country in all available areas. The basic area, of course, remains the assistance provided to war refugees. However, it needs to be noted that Poland - pursuant to the commitments made - is also a country through which the free movement of goods, including agricultural products, from the legal territory of Ukraine takes place. This issue is extremely important from the point of view of creating an appropriate legal framework to protect the Polish agricultural market. This is not possible without appropriate support from the EU. In this regard, it seems necessary to develop appropriate legal mechanisms.

It should also be emphasized that the armed conflict overlapped with the existing threats related to, among others, the energy crisis and the escalating climate change. These issues have a direct impact

on the need to re-evaluate the agricultural policy principles developed so far, both at the national and EU level.

In particular, climate change changes the nature of agricultural production and its structure. In this regard, it is necessary to take action, also in the legislative dimension, aimed at strengthening the legal mechanisms of agricultural production security and food security. In this matter, legal solutions are also necessary, imposing an obligation on individual states to create reserves.

Generally speaking, the Polish legal system, albeit not without shortcomings, is gradually adapting to the outlined challenges, which was mentioned in the course of the Report.

However, it seems that the most important challenge will be the coordination of activities in the analyzed area, at the EU level, taking into account economic, social and legal differences in individual countries. In this matter, it is undoubtedly necessary to accelerate legislative activities.